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Annotation. This article analyzes the issue of pedagogical psychological aspects of socialization of preschool children.

Keywords. Personality, preschool education, psychological research, family, play, willpower.

Preschool education, which is one of the early and main stages in the formation of a person, plays an important role in the development of children psychologically along with their physiologic growth, their formation as a person. The psychologist R., noting that the importance of preschool age in the socialization of children is incomparable. S. Nemov divides this period into three phases [R.S.N., 193]. That is:

- 1) Emotional Self-Management stage (3-4 years);
- 2) morally self-governing stage (4-5 years);
- 3) the stage of formation of personal-practical qualities (5-6 years).

In fact, observing the activities of Educators of preschool institutions at 3-4 years old, they give an assessment from an emotional point of view to the haqea-events taking place around them. For example, if events happen to them that they do not like, they express dissatisfaction, offend and even cry. On the contrary, they rejoice when the event that happened to them is perceived as pleasant, they "report" about it to their peers, parents, other members of the family or educators, they laugh with laughter. When they reach the age of 3, active speech is formed in children and they begin to speak fluently. The growth of speech creates the ground for the development of reason. By engaging in communication with those around them, they understand the environment, nature and the surrounding world better, deeper. This situation in turn contributes to the development of the psyche of children of preschool age. During this period, their mobility, perception of material existence and speech develop at a rapid pace.

Their perception is a real predestined perception, the subjects they perceive, they think about what they are familiar with. The perception of the child during this period is most often expressed in his relationship to the predicates. At the age of preschool education, speech develops in proportion with the development of children's consciousness. In the period from the age of 3 to 6 years, children learn almost all of the vocabulary that is constantly used in everyday life and the simple grammatical methods of the language.

At the age of preschool education, the active interaction of children with the surrounding world – peers and adults – contributes to an increase in their speech wealth. As a result, by this age, they will be able to tell in detail about the events that they have fulfilled, witnessed or heard from others. Relations with those around them have a positive effect on the formation of their personality. As a result of this influence, moral and moral judgments about social realities are decided in them.

In the growth of the emotional qualities of educators and their formation as an individual, the relationship of the surrounding people, especially loved ones, to them, is important. In relation to the children "you are a good

child!", "I love you!", "Believe me, my son (or daughter) does not do bad deeds!" or "my daughter (or son) will hear only thanks from those around!" to say together with the expression of the love of those around them, they are self-worthy ("I'm a good boy!", "I'm a decent girl!", "My dad (mom) loves me!" in style) also trains assessment skills. Words like the above are the greatest praise for children of preschool age. "You are a bad boy!", "You do not listen to what is said!", "If you do the work of a fool!" and to say is the greatest laziness, hindering the development of self-awareness feelings that are formed in them. As a result, the child's soul fades, insecurity appears in relation to himself. In children born in this same spirit, negative qualities are formed and strengthened, such as alienation from the surrounding world, self-reliance, inability to adequately assess their capabilities.

The behavior of children of preschool age is based on emotional arousal, emotional arousal is reflected in their activity, mobility, their reaction to the events taking place around them. Many children at this age "express their achievements or failures by demonstrating their respective emotional reactions in their activities. Most children at this age simply emphasize the result obtained; some accept successes and failures through positive and negative emotions. In this age group, there is a special reflection of self-assessment, mainly after success in activities. The child will not only rejoice in achievements, but will also show a special sense of pride with an imaginative and expressive demonstration of his successes. However, even such a simple self-assessment is hardly noticeable at this age.

It is possible to observe a mass reaction to achievements and failures that reflect self-assessment after children reach the age of 3,5 years. One psychological study showed that three-year-olds have a simple idea of their personal options. ... And four-year-olds will be able to more accurately assess their capabilities" [Nemov, 197].

The formation of a sense of self-assessment in children of preschool age creates an opportunity for them to approach their behavior from a moral point of view. Now they divide the actions committed by themselves or by others into groups in a positive or negative way. They try to assess their actions, including social subjects, by saying "bad" or "good", "possible" or "impossible", "right" or "not right". As a result of the integration of national values into the content of education in family and preschool institutions, "reward" and "sin" are also used as evaluation criteria in children's attitudes towards their behavior and activities of the surrounding people. By saying "it will be a reward to do" or "it will be a sin to do", in most cases, an assessment will be given to the actions of their peers.

"At the pre-school age, children tend to evaluate themselves and others on the basis of their behavior, certain moral norms. They form a somewhat moral sect, as well as a moral self-governing dignity [Nemov, 193].

Preschool education plays a key role in the activities of children of age. They develop emotionally, morally and physically in the means of games. The Games ensure the development of such qualities as creative imagination, mindfulness, resourcefulness and foresight in children of preschool age. At the same time, games are a source of emotional arousal in children and the formation of moral and moral attitudes. During the playing of the game, they feel a trigger, they also simply enjoy success.

And games organized in the bosom of nature not only help children to find practical skills of movement and moral and moral values, but also lay the groundwork for the formation of aesthetic taste in them.

And games that require a creative approach form such skills as drawing pictures in children, making projects (constructions) of different things, as well as various items made of plasticine or clay, as a result of which there are favorable conditions for their emotional, mental and physical development.

And the fact that children's games are played by the majority in them creates and strengthens the need to strive for a team and be with the team. During the games, there will be a desire to be with the team, mutual harmonization of the interests of the team with personal interests will be ensured, the feelings of friendship and friendship will be decided by the toptiradi, which in turn will positively affect the formation of the feuds of children

of preschool age. Therefore, it is worthwhile to pay special attention to the organization of games that contribute to the mental, willpower and emotional development of the child in pre-school educational organizations, families and micromuhit. The inclusion of games with training or, conversely, the effective use of game elements in the training process has a positive effect on their further enrichment. The feeling of self-awareness in the child appears only after he is two years old. At this time, children can say their names, recognize their reflection in the mirror or in the photo. At the age of preschool education, they characterize themselves according to their appearance, but still avoid enlightening the "inner world". At the age of preschool education "the formation of the child's character continues. Its formation occurs on the basis of observation of the characteristic behavior of adults. In the same years, such important personal qualities as Initiative, willpower, independence begin to find a decision. ... Not only in games, but also in other manifestations of activity: proper assessment of oneself, achievements, failures and personal qualities in reading, Labor and circulation, skills and qualifications are formed" [Nemov, 202].

As a result of the study of the activities of families and pre-school educational institutions and the organization of pedagogical observation, it was found out that some educators also observed negative qualities.

The manifestation of negative habits in the behavior and behavior of children in psychological and pedagogical education is recognized as a consequence of the mistakes made in their upbringing, unhealthy relationships in the family, conflicts in the micromuhite, as well as the violence shown by social subjects (parents, family members, strangers and even educators) (manual., 24).

Based on the results of the study of the moral-moral and psychological-willpower aspects of the socialization of Educators of preschool institutions, it is possible to draw the following conclusions::

1. The age of preschool education is considered a favorable period for the upbringing of the first moral, moral and psychological-willed qualities in children.

2. In this age period, the active communication of educators with social subjects creates an opportunity for them to actively form emotional, mental and physical qualities, as well as the formation of speech skills and the ability to self-assess them.

3. Life experiences, which are important in the socialization of the individual, are mastered by children of preschool age on the basis of imitation of Adult Activities, sample study from peers, attitude to social events and phenomena in the process of play, labor and education.

4. The adult's sincere, loving attitude to children is based on self-awareness in them, the correct assessment of their opportunities and the upbringing of such qualities as respect for their own personality, understanding of their dignity, on the contrary, being rude to children, jerking and caressing them in preschool age leads to the formation of such qualities as low self-assessment, inability to And such negative cases show that pedagogically there is a wrong way to socialize them, and their elimination requires great effort and effort.

5. Games have a great influence on the socialization of children of preschool age, they experience such situations as participation in them, mental alertness by observing the rules of the game, observing the activities of peers, enjoying achievements, feeling aesthetic effects; games with the participation of the team contribute to the formation of feelings of friendship and friendship in children.

Hence, the environment in the socialization of Educators of pre-school educational institutions, in particular. the influence of social subjects is considered important in the types of activities characteristic for children of this age – communication, play, labor and education. And their effective use is one of the important socio-pedagogical tasks facing institutions and families of the preschool education system. Particular attention was paid to this aspect of the problem under study during the organization of experimental and test works. About this is told in detail in the next chapter of the work.

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